

Has COVID-19 crowded out medical research resources from non-COVID-19 diseases? ---- Observations from clinical trials

Wenjing Zhao¹ and Jian Du²

¹*cadyzhao@bjmu.edu.cn*

National Institute of Health Data Science, Peking University, Peking (China)
Institute of Medical Technology, Health Science Center of Peking University, Peking (China)

²*dujian@bjmu.edu.cn*

National Institute of Health Data Science, Peking University, Peking (China)

Abstract

The suspension of clinical trials during the COVID-19 pandemic has been discussed widely. But no systemic study has examined the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 on the clinical trials of non-COVID-19 diseases under a well-recognized disease classification system. By acquiring disease-specific trials data from ClinicalTrials.gov and Dimensions, this study explores the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 from the aspects of trials' activeness and efficiency, as well as the scientific collaboration from multiregional clinical trials (MRCTs). In addition to global observation, the USA, China, Japan, the UK are chosen as representative examples to conduct a more fine-grained comparative analysis. Interestingly, our analysis did not reveal substantial crowding-out effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on medical research resources for other diseases. Specifically, the impact of COVID-19 on the quantity of trials for non-COVID-19 diseases varied significantly across nations, in which China displays a pattern that is considerably different from the other three nations. Further, even though the intensified attention on COVID-19 research has been observed, the progression and completion of other diseases' trials has not been significantly impacted by the pandemic. The examination of MRCT also shows that throughout the pandemic, clinical science collaboration among countries has also been intensified.

Keywords

COVID-19, Crowding-Out Effect, Clinical trials, medical research resources

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has shaken up global structures in a range of ways, leaving in its wake an urgent health need that has required rapid and innovative research to control. Clinical trials are research studies performed in people with the goal of evaluating a medical, surgical, or behavioral intervention. They are the primary approach used by researchers to examine whether a new therapy, such as a drug or diet or medical device, is safe and effective in humans (NIH National Institute on Aging, 2020).

The global pandemic presents many predictable challenges in conducting clinical trials, including difficulties with patient recruiting, in-person data collecting and sudden suspension of interventions (Audisio et al., 2022; Ledford, 2021; van Dorn, 2020). The outbreak of COVID-19 has also led to a high concentration of medical and scientific research resources to address public health emergencies, which may be accompanied by a decline in the research intensity of other diseases, that is, the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 on clinical trials of other diseases. Meanwhile, clinical trials are not an exception to the expected increase in the usage of digital technology brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic (Chen et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2020; Upadhaya et al., 2020). Since telemedicine has grown in acceptance and popularity among patients, physicians, and health authorities (Holtz, 2021; Sathian et al., 2020), it is plausible to suppose that the transition from a traditional to a remote digital mode for clinical trials may be beneficial for their continued operation during the pandemic. Nevertheless, there

are many challenges in large-scale clinical trials involved multiple regions, including the increasing pressure on the coordinating center to maintain oversight, lack of workflow standardization across research sites and differences in laws and regulations among different countries (Hashem et al., 2020). Under such a circumstance, it would be of great significance for systematically exploring the crowding-out effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on clinical trials for other diseases.

Assessing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on clinical trials has been drawing increasing attention from scholars in various fields with diverse approaches. Chen et al. (2021) performed semi-structured qualitative interviews, which suggests that while online meetings, remote follow-up, fast medication delivery, and remote monitoring may assure the progress of clinical trials, they cannot completely guarantee the quality as previously. As for the influence of COVID-19 on the initiation of new clinical trials, 50% of the 734 researchers responded that the COVID-19 pandemic has had a considerable impact on the initiation of new clinical trials according to a survey conducted by Medidata (2020), while the almost 35% researchers claimed the pandemic has had little to no effect on the beginning of new studies. As for the quantitative approach, several studies employed trial data from Clinicaltrials.gov and analyzed data from different perspectives (Audisio et al., 2022; Hawila et al., 2021; Margas et al., 2022; Nishiwaki et al., 2021). For instance, Nishiwaki and Ando found that non-COVID-19 trials experienced a significant decrease during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic (Nishiwaki et al., 2021). Hawila and Berg's study indicates a minimal impact of COVID-19 on the number of submitted clinical trials (Hawila et al., 2021).

In general, existing studies have exhibited varying results. Although Clinicaltrials.gov is an international registration platform and that its data are representative, some trial data from national registries, such as Chinese Clinical Trial Register, cannot be disregarded when performing global-level analysis. Moreover, the majority of studies are performed on the level of COVID-19 versus non-COVID-19 trials (Audisio et al., 2022). Few studies have attempted to investigate the crowding-out effect under a more fine-grained disease classification due to the difficulty of precisely identifying clinical trials for various types of diseases. It is also worth noting that utilizing trial data collected at once cannot provide thoroughly comparative analysis on trials' efficiency, since clinical trials databases only present the latest states at the time of data collection. At the same time, with the COVID-19 pandemic profoundly affecting international scientific collaboration pattern and the need for large-scale clinical trials structured according to a master protocol in a coordinated and collaborative manner (Park et al., 2021), few scholars have paid attention to the status quo of multiregional clinical trials (MRCT) for different diseases in the context of the epidemic.

Indeed, understanding the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 on medical resources of various non-COVID-19 disease is extremely challenging because it is influenced by a variety of social, economic and political factors. Clinical trials have, however, provided one potential pathway for observing such an effect from different aspects. To be specific, this study will explore the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 from the aspects of trials' activeness and efficiency, as well as the scientific collaboration from MRCT. In addition to global observation, we select the four of the five most prolific countries of clinical trials as representative examples to conduct a more fine-grained study, namely the USA, China, Japan, the UK.

Data and Method

Data acquisition

In order to thoroughly explore the crowding-out effect of COVID-19 on trials of other diseases from the perspective of activeness, efficiency and MRCT, various fields of trials data, such as the start year, country/region, trial phase and status, the trial outcomes, the number of enrollments, etc., are essential. More importantly, defining and classifying non-COVID-19 diseases in our analysis required gathering associated disease information from each trial. Like previous studies, ClinicalTrials.gov¹ is applied as the primary data source in this study owing to its comprehensiveness and standardization of various fields, as well as its representativeness of clinical trials data globally. ClinicalTrials.gov is a widely used Web-based resource maintained by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) at the National Institutes of Health (NIH) since 2000, which enables quick access to worldwide data on clinical trials on a variety of diseases.

It is well-known that the trial data fields are to show the most recent status at the time of data collection. For instance, recruitment status is the field indicates the current stage of a trial, whether a clinical study is planned, ongoing, or completed. When exploring the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the trials' progress of different diseases, it would be inappropriate to compare recruitment status of trials started before and after 2020 only using trial data obtained at one time, since trials started in different year have varying durations. Obtaining clinical trials initiated before and after the pandemic that had the same duration is of great significance for a comparable analysis of trials' efficiency. We acquired trials data from ClinicalTrials.gov in the format of independent XML files in June 2021 and July 2022 separately, which will be referred to as the 2021 set and 2022 set hereinafter. As a result, trials started in 2019 in the 2021 set and those started in 2020 in the 2022 set can be regarded as two comparable subsets of trials data in this study, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. The comparable trial data subsets

In addition, despite the fact that ClinicalTrials.gov is an international registration platform and that its data are representative, some trial data from national registries cannot be disregarded. Further trial data from Dimensions² were supplemented in order to present a study that is reasonably thorough and capable of generating reliable results for national comparison. Dimensions was launched by Digital Science in January 2018, which is a partly free scholarly database containing multiple types of scientific data, including clinical trials registered with major national registries worldwide. Note that supplemental data from Dimensions was only used for activeness analysis, as the database also did not contain the required fields for subsequent analysis.

¹ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/about-site/background>

² <https://www.dimensions.ai/>

In sum, we gathered our trials data from ClinicalTrials.gov and Dimensions. Regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, clinical trials that began in 2015–2019 and those that began in 2020–2021 were viewed as before-and-after comparisons. It should be noted that because observational and interventional trials have quite distinct experimental designs, only interventional studies are considered in this study.

Diseases mapping

Identifying and categorizing diseases of trial data is the essential procedure for this research. Figure 2 illustrates several important procedures used in diseases mapping.

Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), a biomedical indexing vocabulary maintained by the US National Library of Medicine (NLM), is employed in this study as the key element for disease mapping. As for obtaining relevant MeSH terms of trials, the field named “condition-MeSH” contained in trial data from ClinicalTrials.gov is the primary source. For trials with empty fields of “condition-MeSH” and those supplemented from Dimensions, we used the National Library of Medicine (NLM) Medical Text Indexer (MTI) to extract the corresponding MeSH terms from the abstracts and titles of trials. The MTI is the main product of the NLM’s Indexing Initiative project and has been producing indexing recommendations based on the MeSH vocabulary since 2002 (Mork et al., 2017). The design of the MTI uses the title and abstract of MEDLINE citations to extract MeSH terms. The operating principle and workflow have been introduced in a previous study (L. Zhang et al., 2020).

In terms of the disease classification, Global Health Estimates (GHE) cause category, a hierarchical structure of 4 levels established by WHO (46) according to ICD-10, is applied in this study. The GHE cause category has a hierarchical structure of four levels. Three broad cause groups constitute level 1, respectively: group I—communicable, maternal, perinatal and nutritional conditions (CMNN); group II—noncommunicable diseases (NCD); Group III—injuries. Further, we have divided COVID-19 into a separate category in order to appropriately compare it with CMNN and NCD category. Additionally, we did not include group III (the injuries category) in our analysis since it mostly deals with transportation and intentional/unintentional injuries rather than particular diseases. A detailed explanation of GHE cause category can be found from a previous study (Zhao, Wang, et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Diseases mapping process

The mapping relationship between MeSH and GHE cause category is established by taking advantage from the concordance table between ICD-10 (classification used by WHO) and MeSH terms (Medical Subject Headings) built by Yegros-Yegros et al. (2020). Specifically, the concordance table used in Yegros-Yegros et al. (2020) was designed to retrieve publication data from PubMed, which has the function to automatically search both the MeSH headings as well as the subordinate terms beneath that heading in the MeSH hierarchy, namely ‘automatic explosion’. For the purpose of mapping diseases to trial data, we first supplement all subordinate terms for each MeSH term in the concordance table according to MeSH hierarchy³. Moreover, manual examination of each MeSH extracted from trial data that was not recognized as a disease by the extended mapping relationship was carried out. Manual examination also further ensure that no subordinate word was concurrently categorized into more than one disease. It should be noted that a full-count assignment scheme has been applied in calculating the number of trials for each disease, that is, trials count of each diseases expressed how many trials the disease has been labeled.

It is worth noting that MTI is also capable of processing arbitrary biomedical texts to provide an ordered list of MeSH terms. Such a process can enable the disease mapping for multiple types of scientific data (publications, grants, patents, etc.) when used with the extended

³ https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/intro_trees.html

mapping relationship between MeSH terms and GHE cause category established in this study. Overall, the number of clinical trials obtained and utilized for this study is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Number of clinical trials from two data sources

	ClinicalTrials.gov		Dimensions	
	2015-2019	2020-2021	2015-2019	2020-2021
Number of trials	133920	64639	251657	133087
Number of interventional trials	103482	47711	150780	71711
Number of interventional trials with diseases	63351	30719	79023	40349

Results and Analysis

Activeness

In this study, we characterize the disease-specific trials' activeness using the total number of clinical trials started before-and-after the pandemic for each disease. Figure 3 demonstrates the number of clinical trials by disease category from 2015 to 2021 worldwide and for four countries. The USA, China and Japan are the three countries with the largest number of trials. The USA ranks first in all categories of disease. Within each disease, the distribution patterns across disease categories are quite similar, i.e., a higher proportion of publications on NCD than for CMNN.

Figure 3. Number of clinical trials by disease category in 2015-2021

Regarding the dynamic trends, the overall number of trials has increased steadily over the previous 7 years on a global scale. The global trial activeness does not seem to have been significantly impacted by the pandemic. The rise in CMNN and COVID-19 trials during the first year of the pandemic is entirely expected. The number of NCD trials did not rise globally

in 2020. In particular, the number of NCD trials in the USA, the UK, and Japan all drastically decreased in 2020 by 13.80%, 20.32%, and 33.84%, respectively. Be aware that from 2018, there have been fewer trials in Japan, and that this drop peaked in 2020. In contrast to the other three countries, China exhibits a quite distinct pattern. While the pandemic has resulted in a decline in the number of NCD trials in other nations, China has seen a notable increase in all diseases' trials. China is the only nation where the number of NCD and CMNN trials has risen during the epidemic. The growth in NCD trials in China was also a major factor in the comparatively low declining rate of NCD trials worldwide (0.14%).

The growth rate showed in figure 4 presents a more detailed picture of COVID-19's crowding-out effect on the activeness of other diseases' trials. Note that two subtypes of NCD (Endocrine, blood, immune disorders, sudden infant death syndrome) and one that of CMNN (Nutritional deficiencies) are excluded in figure 2 due to their limited number of trials (less than 100 trials per year). In general, the rising trend of the number of trials on most NCD subtypes were "interrupted" by the outbreak of COVID-19 in 2020. As for the CMNN, the correlation between COVID-19 and respiratory infections has naturally increased the number of trials. The disease with the most trials was malignant neoplasms, which accounts for more than 25% of all disorders. Unexpectedly, trials of this disease's growing tendency persisted in 2020. Digging deeper into the data, China's significant increase in neoplasms trials in 2020 (up 47.44%) is the main driver of the ongoing global increase in neoplasms trials, which is in contrast to a decline in cancer trials in all other nations. Notably, this conclusion persisted even after trials with COVID-19 and neoplasms comorbidities were disregarded.

Figure 4. Growth rate of clinical trials by disease globally

In all countries, the quantity of COVID-19-related trials declined in 2021 to varying degrees. And the NCD trials' activeness in the USA, the UK and Japan shown a recovery pattern relative to 2020, whereas it sharply declined in China. In general, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a minimal crowding-out effect on the activeness of NCD trials, but the pattern of this effect varies greatly among nations and specific NCD diseases.

Efficiency

This study defines the efficiency of a trial from two aspects: speed and scale. Specifically, the field "recruitment status" can be used to analyze if the pandemic hampered the trial's progress in the analysis of trials speed. The term 'scale' in this context refers to the number of participants in one trial. The analysis on scale focused on whether the epidemic and the imposition of quarantine restrictions have altered the trial's enrollment scale.

(1) Speed

Figure 5 demonstrates the distribution of trials' status by disease and by country, using two comparable subsets of trials data (figure 1) before-and-after the pandemic. With the exception of COVID-19, most clinical trials of NCD and CMNN are in the status of "recruiting". More than 43% COVID-19 trials have been completed in 2 years, which is a significant indication of the intensive and effective efforts contributed by academia to address the pandemic. However, the distribution of trials' status is basically consistent from both country and disease perspectives, suggesting that COVID-19 has no significant impact on trial speed of other diseases. That is to say, even while researchers have worked tirelessly and effectively to control the outbreak, the progression of other diseases studies has not been significantly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 5. Distribution of status by disease and by country

(2) Scale

The enrollment scale in clinical trials varies considerably for a variety of reasons, one of which is the trial phase, which plays a significant role in determining the enrollment scale. For instance, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) offers suggestions for the enrollment scale for various trial stages (U.S. Food & Drug Administration, 2018). This study divided the number of enrollment into the 6 segments by referring to the recommendation from the FDA (0; 1-20; 21-100; 101-300; 301-3000 ;>3000), as shown in Figure 6. It is important to note that the

enrollment information offered by ClinicalTrials.gov for the recruiting status of “completed” and other types of trials differs. Enrollment for “completed” studies refers to the actual participants in the trial, whereas for other types of trials, it refers to the target number of participants. The completed trials are applied here to accurately reflect the enrollment scale.

Figure 6. Distribution of actual enrollment scale of completed trials by phase globally

Figure 6 depicts the distribution of actual enrollment scale by phase, which illustrates quite distinct patterns in the five phases. From the viewpoint of before-and-after pandemic comparisons, there was no structural change in the fraction of trials with varied scales for any of the five phases. Nevertheless, in all five phases, the fraction of scale with 1~20 participants reduced, which in part suggested a little widening of the enrollment scale. In addition, studies involving more than 3000 volunteers have been conducted in all four nations (the USA, the UK, China, and Japan) since the pandemic. Nearly 50 percent of the 73 studies with more than 3000 participants were COVID-19 trials. The number of enrollment by disease category, as shown in table 2, makes this tendency easier to see. Obviously, compared to NCD and CMNN, COVID-19 has a significantly greater average participant count. Furthermore, enrollment of NCD and CMNN also improved even when trials on COVID-19 and NCD/CMNN comorbidities were excluded from the calculation of the average number of participants for these two categories.

Table 2. Average number of enrollment of completed trials by disease category

	NCD	CMNN	COVID-19
Before	98	224	\
After	115	236	348

Notes: 1) trials with more than 10000 participants were removed;
 2) trials on COVID-19 and NCD/CMNN comorbidities were removed when calculating the average number of enrollment for NCD and CMNN.

Multiregional Clinical Trials (MRCTs)

A clinical trial defined as an MRCT is one that is conducted under a single protocol in more than one region (ICH, 2018). A significant advantage of MRCTs is the acceleration of global clinical development and the facilitation of registration in every part of the world, which can enable the worldwide distribution of novel medications to patients as quickly as is scientifically possible. Similar to co-authored academic papers, MRCT is also a vital form of medical research collaboration. According to Fry et al. (2020), the geographic loci of coronavirus research generally, as well as the structure of academic teams, were shifted by the onset of COVID-19. Yet, although most studies on COVID-19 involve collaborative analysis with publication data (Pathak, 2020; Wu et al., 2021; Lin Zhang et al., 2020), little attention has been given to examining the collaboration patterns exhibited by clinical trial data.

The identification and calculation of MRCTs can be performed by utilizing the field “Locations” and extracting country information in trial data. Figure 7 presents the proportional changes in MRCTs by country/region. With an average percentage of MRCTs of 8.69% between 2015 and 2019, the great majority of trials are carried out independently globally. Only China has a lower percentage of MRCTs than the global average. It is noteworthy that half of the clinical trials conducted in the UK and Japan during the COVID-19 pandemic were MRCTs. The finding sheds light on the fluctuating trends observed in the number of trials conducted in these two countries, as illustrated in Figure 3. In contrast to the US, both the UK and Japan have a comparatively lower number of trials, with a considerable proportion of them being international collaborations. Owing to the smaller scale and preponderance of cooperative trials, multiple factors are likely to influence the magnitude of changes, thereby making it easier to demonstrate significant variations.

From 2015 to 2019, the percentage of MRCT continuously decreased globally. Yet again, the COVID-19 pandemic “interrupted” this downward trend. That is, a significant increase on the MRCT percentage was seen in 2020, and this tendency was observed in all four nations, indicating strengthened collaboration among countries with academic capabilities. Further, most MRCTs are conducted with involvement from two to four countries. Our results also demonstrate that COVID-19-related MRCTs involve, on average, fewer countries than NCD and CMNN, which is consistent with Fry's finding of narrowing team membership in coronavirus research during the COVID-19 pandemic. The preference for strong alliances among countries with solid research capacities when responding to emergent outbreaks may be one factor contributing to the “shrinking scale” of collaboration (Fry et al., 2020; Zhao, Zhang, et al., 2022).

In general, our results provide another strong piece of evidence that collaboration among countries with academic capabilities in research and innovation has intensified during the pandemic (Guimon et al., 2022), in addition to the results from previous studies using publications data.

Figure 7. Proportion of MRCTs by country/region in 2015-2021

A further observation is provided from the perspective of national comparative analysis, as shown by figure 8. Compared to the USA, which participated in 65% of the MRCTS worldwide, China only participated in less than 8% of them. China has progressively boosted its involvement in the worldwide MRCT since the China Food and Drug Administration (CFDA, now known as National Medical Products Administration) joined the ICH⁴ in 2017 (WCG FDAnews, 2017). In addition to independent trials, bilateral collaboration is the most common type of MRCT for China and the USA, whereas the UK and Japan have engaged more in MRCTs with a greater number of countries.

Figure 8. Global share of MRCTs of each country in 2015-2021

Conclusion and Discussion

Summary

In this study, we explored the crowding-out effect on medical research resources of COVID-19 on other non-COVID-19 diseases by utilizing clinical trial data. In particular, the crowding-out effect were analyzed from the aspects of trials' activeness and efficiency, as well as the

⁴ The International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH)

scientific collaboration from MRCT. In addition to global observation, the USA, China, Japan, the UK are chosen as representative examples to conduct a more fine-grained comparative study.

Contrary to the assumption that COVID-19 might significantly affect the research resources allocation for existing diseases, our analysis, which was based on data from clinical trials, did not reveal substantial crowding-out effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on medical research resources for other disease. Our results certainly reflect the increased interest in COVID-19 brought on by the pandemic, indicating by extensive trial implementation, higher trial completion rates, and larger enrollment scale. Globally, however, the tremendous attention paid to COVID-19 has not had remarkable crowding-out effects on the activeness, efficiency, or international collaborations of trials for other disorders.

Specifically, analysis of activeness shows that the impact of COVID-19 on the quantity of trials for non-COVID-19 diseases varied significantly across nations. China displays a pattern that is considerably different from the other three nations—a notable rise in both NCD and CMNN trials. In terms of the efficiency analysis, we discovered that even though researchers have been working intensively on COVID-19 to contain the outbreak, the progression and completion of other diseases trials has not been significantly impacted by the pandemic. Moreover, following the pandemic, a little expansion of the enrollment scale for both NCD and CMNN trials was observed. The examination of MRCT also shows that throughout the pandemic, collaboration among countries with academic capacities for research and innovation has intensified.

Overall, the observed differences in countries' responses (e.g., China vs. other countries), the digitalization of clinical trials, and the differentiated roles of various sponsors (industry vs. non-industry) might all be contributing factors to our results. Specifically, the negligible variation in the number of non-communicable disease trials observed globally could be attributed to China's increasing number of trials and other countries' decreasing number of trials, effectively neutralizing each other. Additionally, the digitalization of clinical trials presents new opportunities for improving trial efficiency, such as enabling remote patient monitoring and enhancing the quality, quantity, and frequency of data collection (Garg et al., 2018). A prior study published in *NPJ Digital Medicine* has demonstrated a significant growth in the utilization of connected digital products in clinical studies (Marra et al., 2020). This trend is anticipated to persist during the pandemic as efforts are made to mitigate COVID-19 related challenges, such as the issued "virtual" clinical trial guidance issued by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) early in the pandemic (FDA, 2020).

In the context of the global pandemic, international collaborations are essential for scholars to enhance their research abilities. As previously stated, our finding of intensified collaboration among countries with academic capacities aligns with prior research generated by publication data (Fry et al., 2020). Moreover, the digitalization of clinical trials may lower the cost of collaborations, which could be an additional incentive for intensified collaboration. With regard to the distinct roles of various sponsors, studies on clinical trial sponsor type have indicated that the patterns of industry and non-industry sponsored trials differ widely (Atal et al., 2015; Cooper et al., 2021). Therefore, we argue that different sponsors might play different roles in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic, indirectly affecting the number of trials for various diseases. Consequently, the considerable increase in COVID-19-related clinical trials during the pandemic was primarily due to a "ramp up" of researchers' and academia's effort rather than a crowding out of research on other diseases. Investigating the reasons underlying our observational results could be an intriguing avenue for future research.

In sum, this paper makes three contributions. First, it provided an updated study and comparison of clinical trials initiated before-and-after the COVID-19 pandemic with worldwide trial data, leading to some new discoveries regarding the COVID-19's crowding-out effect on medical research resources for non-COVID-19 diseases. Second, by employing the MTI and establishing the mapping relationship between MeSH term and GHE cause category, this study identified disease-specific trials and attempted to investigate the crowding-out effect under a more fine-grained disease classification. It is worth noting that the methods and tools used in this study can be further applied to analyse the allocation of research resource on different diseases in a broader range with different types of data. Third, the analysis of MRCT performed in this study provide additional evidence on intensified scientific collaboration among countries with academic capabilities, in addition to previous studies using publications data.

Limitation

Two limitations need to be addressed in this study. The first one is the data related limitation. With the aim of contributing a relatively comprehensive and systematic analysis of the clinical trial before-and-after the pandemic, we drew our trial corpus from ClinicalTrials.gov and Dimensions. Although trial data from the major national registration platforms on clinical trials are included, certain trials might have been missed due to registration, location and other reasons. Additionally, we used the concordance table between ICD-10 and MeSH terms from Yegros-Yegros et al (2020), which was approved by a medical doctor, to guarantee the accuracy of mapping relationships between MeSH terms and GHE cause categories. Although we included additional subordinate terms based on MeSH hierarchy and manual examination to our mapping relationship, certain trials with MeSH terms related to no particular diseases will have been neglected.

References

- Atal, I., Trinquart, L., Porcher, R., et al. (2015). Differential Globalization of Industry- and Non-Industry-Sponsored Clinical Trials. *PLoS One*, *10*(12), e0145122. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0145122
- Audisio, K., Lia, H., Robinson, N. B., et al. (2022). Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Non-COVID-19 Clinical Trials. *J Cardiovasc Dev Dis*, *9*(1). doi:10.3390/jcdd9010019
- Chen, Z., Chen, L., & Chen, H. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on the clinical trial. *PLoS One*, *16*(5), e0251410. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0251410
- Cooper, L., Lee, I., & Waldron Lechner, D. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic response varies by clinical trial sponsor type. *Journal of Clinical Translational Science*, *5*(1), e111. doi:10.1017/cts.2021.25
- FDA. (2020). *Guidance on Conduct of Clinical Trials of Medical Products during COVID-19 Public Health Emergency*. Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/media/136238/download>
- Fry, C., Cai, X., Zhang, Y., et al. (2020). Consolidation in a crisis: Patterns of international collaboration in early COVID-19 research. *PLoS One*, *15*(7), e0236307.
- Garg, S., Williams, N., Ip, A., et al. (2018). Clinical integration of digital solutions in health care: an overview of the current landscape of digital technologies in cancer care. *JCO Clinical Cancer Informatics*, *2*, 2473–4276.
- Guimon, J., & Narula, R. (2022). A happy exception: The pandemic is driving global scientific collaboration. Retrieved from <https://issues.org/pandemic-global-scientific-collaboration/>
- Hashem, H., Abufaraj, M., Tbakhi, A., et al. (2020). Obstacles and Considerations Related to Clinical Trial Research During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Front Med (Lausanne)*, *7*, 598038. doi:10.3389/fmed.2020.598038
- Hawila, N., & Berg, A. (2021). Assessing the impact of COVID-19 on registered interventional clinical trials. *Clin Transl Sci*, *14*(3), 1147–1154. doi:10.1111/cts.13034
- Holtz, B. (2021). Patients perceptions of telemedicine visits before and after the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. , *27*(1), 107–112. *Telemedicine Journal and E-health : the official journal of the American Telemedicine Association*, *27*(1), 107-112.

- ICH. (2018). *E17 General Principles for Planning and Design of Multiregional Clinical Trials*. Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/media/99974/download>
- Ledford, H. (2021, 28 June 2021). The COVID pandemic's lingering impact on clinical trials.
- Margas, W., Wojciechowski, P., & Toumi, M. (2022). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the conduct of clinical trials: a quantitative analysis. *J Mark Access Health Policy*, 10(1), 2106627. doi:10.1080/20016689.2022.2106627
- Marra, C., Chen, J. L., Coravos, A., et al. (2020). Quantifying the use of connected digital products in clinical research. *NPJ Digit Med*, 3, 50. doi:10.1038/s41746-020-0259-x
- Medidata (Producer). (2020, 07 November 2022). COVID- 19 and clinical trials: the Medidata perspective. *BMJ*.
- Mork, J. G., Aronson, A., & Demner-Fushman, D. (2017). 12 years on – Is the NLM medical text indexer still useful and relevant? *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 8(1), 1-10.
- NIH National Institute on Aging. (2020). What are clinical trials and studies? Retrieved from <https://www.nia.nih.gov/health/what-are-clinical-trials-and-studies>.
<https://www.nia.nih.gov/health/what-are-clinical-trials-and-studies>
- Nishiwaki, S., & Ando, Y. (2021). COVID-19 Pandemic and Trends in Clinical Trials: A Multi-Region and Global Perspective. *Front Med (Lausanne)*, 8, 812370. doi:10.3389/fmed.2021.812370
- Park, J. J. H., Mogg, R., Smith, G. E., et al. (2021). How COVID-19 has fundamentally changed clinical research in global health. *The Lancet Global Health*, 9(5), e711-e720. doi:10.1016/s2214-109x(20)30542-8
- Pathak, M. (2020). Quantitative analysis of international collaboration on COVID-19: Indian perspective. *Indian Journal of Biochemistry & Biophysics*, 57(4), 439-443. Retrieved from <Go to ISI>://WOS:000555697800009
- Sathian, B., Asim, M., Banerjee, I., et al. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on clinical trials and clinical research: A systematic review. *Nepal J Epidemiol*, 10(3), 878-887. doi:10.3126/nje.v10i3.31622
- Smith, A. C., Thomas, E., Snoswell, C. L., et al. (2020). Telehealth for global emergencies: Implications for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Journal of Telemedicine and Telecare*, 26(5), 309–313.
- U.S. Food & Drug Administration. (2018). Step 3: Clinical Research. Retrieved from <https://www.fda.gov/patients/drug-development-process/step-3-clinical-research>
- Upadhaya, S., Yu, J. X., Oliva, C., et al. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on oncology clinical trials. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*, 19(6), 376-377. doi:10.1038/d41573-020-00093-1
- van Dorn, A. (2020). COVID-19 and readjusting clinical trials. *the Lancet*, 396(10250), 523-524.
- WCG FDAnews (Producer). (2017, 29 October 2022). China Joins ICH as Full Regulatory Member, Pledges to Implement Guidelines.
- Wu, L. Y., Yang, J. Q., Wang, D., et al. (2021). Scientists' response to global public health emergencies: A bibliometrics perspective. *Journal of Information Science*, 1-21. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211030866>
- Yegros-Yegros, A., van de Klippe, W., Abad-Garcia, M. F., et al. (2020). Exploring why global health needs are unmet by research efforts: the potential influences of geography, industry and publication incentives. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 18(1), 1-14. doi:10.1186/s12961-020-00560-6
- Zhang, L., Zhao, W., Liu, J., et al. (2020). Do national funding organizations properly address the diseases with the highest burden?: Observations from China and the UK. *Scientometrics*, 125(2), 1733-1761. doi:10.1007/s11192-020-03572-9
- Zhang, L., Zhao, W., Sun, B., et al. (2020). How scientific research reacts to international public health emergencies: a global analysis of response patterns. *Scientometrics*, 124(1), 747-773.
- Zhao, W., Wang, L., & Zhang, L. (2022). How does academia respond to the burden of infectious and parasitic disease? *Health Research Policy System*, 20(1), 89. doi:10.1186/s12961-022-00889-0
- Zhao, W., Zhang, L., Wang, J., et al. (2022). How has academia responded to the urgent needs created by COVID-19? – A multi-level global, regional and national analysis. *Journal of Information Science*, 1-33. doi:DOI: 10.1177/01655515221084646